

USE OF RESONANT ULTRASONIC SPECTROSCOPY IN ELASTIC CONSTANT MEASUREMENT OF DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED TITANIUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Resonant ultrasonic spectroscopy (RUS) is based on the principle that mechanical resonances generated in a solid are dependent upon the geometry, density, crystal structure, and elastic constants. The application of RUS to determine the elastic constants C_{ij} of discontinuously reinforced titanium (DRTi) composites is evaluated in this study. DRTi materials comprising Ti-6Al-4V matrix discontinuously reinforced with TiB whiskers were produced using powder metallurgy approaches and thermomechanical processing was performed using blind-die compaction and extrusion to obtain a variety of microstructures. The volume fraction of TiB is varied in the range 10-40% to study its effect on the stiffness of DRTi. In the blind-die compacted condition, TiB is randomly oriented in an equiaxed $\alpha+\beta$ matrix and the material was modeled as isotropic to determine the C_{ij} 's using RUS. In the extruded condition, on the other hand, TiB is aligned along the extrusion direction and these materials are modeled as transversely isotropic to determine C_{ij} 's in the longitudinal as well as transverse directions. These results show a significant increase in stiffness (up to ~90%) with increasing volume fraction of TiB. A small anisotropy is measured for samples with aligned whiskers. The stiffness values obtained from RUS are in close agreement with those obtained from the mechanical testing.

Keywords: resonance, ultrasound, TiB, discontinuously reinforced titanium, elastic constant

1. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced titanium (DRTi) composites containing titanium monoboride (TiB) whiskers are emerging as potential replacement materials for applications requiring high specific stiffness and strength properties [1]. Though titanium alloys are currently meeting the requirements of many design considerations, improvements in stiffness coupled with tighter design margins provide significant opportunities for the metal matrix composites. Interest in DRTi composites is relatively new, but is definitely not in its infancy, as commercial use of these materials became reality in 1998 when Toyota Motor Company utilized them for both intake and exhaust valves [2]. Indeed, much potential also exists for the use of DRTi in the aerospace community. However, more research needs to be conducted and the improvements in mechanical property combinations are to be demonstrated for employing DRTi in such applications. Further, accurate determination of the properties is important in the developmental effort of these materials for a variety of applications. Therefore, the objective of this study is to determine the stiffness of these materials and understand the role of variables such as reinforcement volume fraction, orientation, size and distribution, and matrix microstructure in improving the stiffness. Another objective is to demonstrate an effective and reliable means by which the elastic properties of DRTi composites can

be analyzed using resonant ultrasonic spectroscopy (RUS), a non-destructive technique. DRTi materials having Ti-6Al-4V matrix and TiB whisker reinforcement produced by powder metallurgy techniques were considered. Thermomechanical processing (TMP) was conducted to modify the microstructural characteristics. The stiffness of these materials were determined using RUS. Stiffness measurements from conventional tensile tests were also performed on these materials and are compared with the values obtained from RUS.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Ti-6Al-4V/TiB Materials Fabrication

Ti-6Al-4V/TiB materials were produced via two powder metallurgy techniques, viz. blended elemental (BE) and pre-alloyed (PA). The BE composites were prepared [3] by blending appropriate amounts of commercially available powders of Ti-6Al-4V (average particle size 30 μm), Ti (average particle size 30 μm) and TiB₂ (average particle size 15 μm) in n-butanol medium using turbula mixer for 24 hours. The blended powder mixture of about 1 kg was packed into a thick-walled (6.35 mm), 70 mm diameter and 130 mm long can made of commercially pure Ti-6Al-4V, vacuum outgassed at 300°C for 24 hours, and sealed by crimp and weld. The can was heated to 1200° C, soaked for 1 hour, and then blind-die compacted (BDC) in an extrusion chamber heated to 260°C. The compact was held at pressure of 1500 MPa for 180 seconds, and subsequently air-cooled to room temperature. The compact was subjected to a heat treatment at 1300°C for 6 h in order to fully convert TiB₂ into TiB as per the *in situ* chemical reaction

One set of heat treated billets were subjected to a round-to-round extrusion after soaking at 1300°C for 1 h and using 13:1 extrusion ratio. A ram speed of 8.5 mm s⁻¹ for the 20 vol.% TiB composite and 17 mm s⁻¹ for the 40 vol.% TiB composite was used.

In the PA approach, -35 mesh (<500 μm) and -100 mesh (<150 μm) Ti-6Al-4V/TiB powders were prepared by argon gas-atomization. Boron additions were made in the form of TiB₂ that dissolves in the melt and TiB formation occurs during solidification. Blind-die compaction of these powders was conducted using identical process parameters used for BE composites. Extrusions were performed at 1100°C using an extrusion ratio of 16.7:1 and a ram speed of 6 mm s⁻¹. Microstructural characterization of the materials produced was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in the backscatter electron imaging mode. A summary of the microstructural characteristics of all the materials used in this study is given in Table 1.

Table 1 Microstructural characteristics of DRTi composites used in this study

Composition	Powder Technique	Vol.% TiB	TiB Orientation	Typical TiB Length (μm)	Typical TiB Aspect Ratio	Matrix Grain Size (μm)
Ti-6Al-4V-1.6B	PA	10	Random	12	10	3
			Aligned			
Ti-6Al-4V-1.7B	PA	12	Aligned	15	10	5
Ti-6Al-4V/20TiB	BE	20	Aligned	22.2	5	15
			Random			
Ti-6Al-4V/40TiB	BE	40	Aligned	13.5	2.5	20

2.2 Elastic Constant Measurements using RUS

Parallelepiped specimens of dimensions 3mm x 4mm x 5mm were machined from the composite materials via electro-discharge machining (EDM) and polished to a 15 μm finish on all sides. The specimens were then individually mounted as shown in Figure 1 between two transducers of a centimeter stage RUS unit (manufactured by Dynamic Resonance System Inc). The system also consists of C++ based computer software to perform the computations involved in the determination of the elastic constants. It has been demonstrated [4] that elastic constant measurements with an error of 0.02-3% can be accomplished through RUS, and therefore this technique has the potential of significantly smaller error as compared to conventional mechanical testing techniques. The theory and associated equations [5-9] used in determining the elastic constants of DRTi using RUS are given in the Appendix.

Figure 1 RUS test setup showing parallelepiped shaped specimen held by transducers used to determine elastic constants.

2.3 Tensile Testing

Room temperature tensile testing was conducted using 2.4 mm thick flat dog bone type specimens having a width of 5.6 mm and 25 mm length in the gauge portion. A 10 mm gauge length extensometer was used to measure the elongation and tests were performed at a crosshead speed of $8 \times 10^{-4} \text{mm s}^{-1}$ up to 0.2% strain and then at $8 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm s}^{-1}$ until fracture.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DRTi Microstructures

A typical microstructure of a PA Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB composite in the compacted condition is shown in Figure 2, which reveals uniform distribution and random orientation of TiB whiskers in an equiaxed $\alpha+\beta$ matrix. Figure 3 shows typical microstructures of the PA extruded composite in the longitudinal and transverse directions. After extrusion, TiB is primarily oriented along the extrusion direction. The majority of TiB in the PA composites is in the form of eutectic needles typically 10-15 μm in length, with an aspect ratio of 10. Figures 2 and 3 show the presence of a small volume fraction of submicron size whiskers of TiB with an average length of 0.5 μm and aspect ratio of 10. A few isolated coarse particles of primary TiB are also present in PA composites. Figure 4 shows a microstructure of BE Ti-6Al-4V/20 vol.% TiB extruded composite in the longitudinal and transverse directions. When compared with PA materials, both the TiB and matrix grain size are coarser in BE composites. The matrix grain size in the PA materials is typically 3-5 μm while it is 15-20 μm in the BE composites. Representative microstructures of a BE Ti-6Al-4V/40 vol.% TiB extruded composite in the longitudinal and transverse directions are shown in Figure 5.

3.2 Stiffness of DRTi Composites

Using the method of RUS and the equations cited in the Appendix, the Young' modulus, E , of Ti-6Al-4V/TiB composites have been determined by assuming randomly oriented TiB composites as isotropic and aligned TiB composites as transversely isotropic [5]. The values obtained for different composites are shown as a function of volume fraction of TiB, V_f^{TiB} , in Figure 6. For comparison, the values obtained from tensile testing are also presented in this figure, which shows close agreement. For example, in 20

V_f^{TiB} randomly distributed TiB composite produced via BE approach, E determined from RUS is 161 GPa while it is 145 GPa from tensile testing. As indicated in Figure 6, this compares to approximately 109 GPa for standard mill-annealed Ti-6Al-4V alloy, which is almost a 50% improvement in stiffness due to TiB reinforcement. In samples with aligned TiB whiskers of $V_f^{TiB} = 20\%$ results in stiffness values of 168 and 154 in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. The stiffness of BE extruded DRTi composite with 40% V_f^{TiB} is 200 GPa and 188 GPa in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively, providing a substantial increase of ~90% in overall stiffness as compared to standard mill-annealed Ti-6Al-4V. In the extruded materials, a small decrease in stiffness occurs in the direction perpendicular to the whisker alignment (i.e. extrusion direction), and this difference increases slightly with increasing V_f^{TiB} (Figure 6). The stiffness increase as a function of V_f^{TiB} approximately follows the rule of mixtures. A smaller error (< RMS 0.2%) is associated with the RUS data as compared to $\pm 2\%$ in the typical tensile test data.

Figure 2 Typical microstructure of PA Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB composite in the compacted condition showing random orientation of TiB whiskers. The gray background is the α matrix, the bright phase is β and the dark phase is TiB.

Figure 3 Typical microstructure of PA Ti-6Al-4V/10 vol.% TiB composite in the extruded condition in the (a) longitudinal and (b) transverse direction. The gray background is the α matrix, the bright phase is β and the dark phase is TiB. Extrusion direction is vertical in (a).

Figure 4 Typical microstructures for Ti-6Al-4V/20% vol TiB composite with TiB whiskers in an aligned arrangement produced via BE and subsequent BDC and extrusion, shown in the (a) longitudinal direction and (b) transverse direction. Extrusion direction is vertical in (a).

Figure 5 Typical microstructures for Ti-6Al-4V/40% vol TiB composite with TiB whiskers in an aligned arrangement produced via BE and subsequent BDC and extrusion, shown in the (a) longitudinal direction and (b) transverse direction. Extrusion direction is vertical in (a).

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Ti-6Al-4V/TiB composites were produced via blended elemental and prealloyed powder metallurgy techniques in combination with thermomechanical processing in order to create a fully dense product with random or aligned TiB whiskers within an equiaxed $\alpha+\beta$ matrix. Resonant ultrasonic spectroscopy (RUS) was utilized to determine the elastic constants from which the stiffness characteristics of the DRTi composites were evaluated as a function of increasing TiB volume fraction and orientation. The following conclusions are drawn from this study:

- DRTi with up to 40 vol.% TiB reinforcement resulted in improvements in Young's modulus up to 90% compared to unreinforced mill-annealed Ti-6Al-4V.

- Good agreement between the stiffness values of DRTi composites determined from RUS and mechanical testing exists.
- Modulus values in the transverse direction are slightly lower than those in the longitudinal direction for composites with TiB aligned along the extrusion direction and the difference increases with increasing volume fraction of TiB.
- RUS is a useful and reliable tool for determining the stiffness of DRTi composites with random or aligned whiskers with relatively small errors.
- The ability to make non-destructive measurements using very small specimens allows analysis of material in the transverse direction for limited material product size produced, which gives a distinct advantage over standard mechanical test techniques.

Figure 6 Comparison of Young's modulus evaluated by tensile test and RUS method as a function of volume fraction and orientation of TiB in Ti-6A-4V/TiB composites. PA: pre-alloyed, BE: blended elemental. (rms error < 0.2% for RUS data)

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APPENDIX: EVALUATION OF ELASTIC CONSTANTS USING RUS

Resonant ultrasound spectroscopy (RUS) is based on the principle that mechanical resonances of a solid are dependent upon geometry, density, crystal structure, and elastic constants. Since the elastic constants are sensitive to changes in composition and temperature, or changes in the crystal structure, RUS is a powerful tool for materials characterization.

To obtain the elastic constants of the material, the specimen is mounted on the RUS unit (Figure 1) and excited by a transducer over a specified input frequency range, and the corresponding specimen amplitudes are output. Figure 7 shows a typical scan spectrum from a DRTi composite specimen used in this study. The highest amplitudes shown correspond to the natural excitation frequencies of the specific material sample. By analyzing a set of excitation peaks over a broad range of input frequencies, the elastic constants can be fit using a typical RMS method, and finally determined to have a particular RMS fit error. A fit is considered good if a final RMS % error value close to 0.2 is achieved.

Figure 7 Typical RUS output spectrum of a DRTi composite.

In both the PA and BE approaches, the as-extruded material was modeled as transversely isotropic, while the as-compacted material was considered to be isotropic [6]. Through the use of a RUS analysis, the five elastic constants for the material with aligned TiB whiskers were determined. A relationship was established with the compliance constants whereby the dynamic elastic modulus in the transverse E_T and longitudinal E_L directions could be calculated. For the material with randomly distributed TiB whiskers, an isotropic assumption allowed for a direct means of attaining the elastic modulus, E , through known equations relating the elastic constants and moduli [6]. The elastic stiffness tensor C_{ij} is given by

$$C_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{11} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{13} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{C_{11} - C_{12}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (A1)$$

The C_{ij} and its inverse the elastic compliance, S_{ij} , are related to the stress σ and strain ε by the relations

$$\sigma_{ij} = \Sigma C_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (A2)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \Sigma S_{ij} \sigma_{ij} \quad (A3)$$

In the case of blind die compacted DRTi composites with evenly dispersed TiB whiskers, the assumption of isotropy is valid, and there are only two independent elastic constants, viz. C_{11} and C_{44} . From the pre-determined elastic constants from the RUS output, the specific elastic moduli can be calculated from the following relationship equations as given by Schreiber [6].

$$G = C_{44} \quad (A4)$$

$$\lambda = C_{12} \quad (A5)$$

$$L = \lambda + 2G \quad (A6)$$

$$B = \lambda + 2G/3 \quad (A7)$$

$$V = \lambda / 2(\lambda + G) \quad (A8)$$

$$E = (3\lambda + 2G) / (\lambda + G) \quad (A9)$$

where G , λ , L , B , ν , and E are the shear modulus, Lamé' constant, longitudinal modulus, bulk modulus, Poisson's ratio, and Young's Modulus, respectively.

For an anisotropic material, which is the case of DRTi composites having aligned TiB whiskers, a different set of equations needs to be utilized for determining the stiffness. In evaluating DRTi with unidirectional TiB whiskers, the material is assumed to be of hexagonally transverse isotropic symmetry where the axis of transverse isotropy (i.e. the whisker reinforcement direction) is taken to be the z direction [8] and the quantity of independent elastic constants are five, which are determined using the following equations [7].

$$S_{11}(1-a_3^2) + S_{33} a_3^4 + (2S_{13} + S_{44})(a_3 - a_3^4) \quad (A10)$$

The direction of interest [hkl] within the crystal relates the angle cosines a_1 , a_2 , a_3 with the x , y , and z axes. The above equation can be adapted to derive the following equations for Young's modulus in the longitudinal (E_L) and transverse (E_T) directions, which are given by

$$E_L = C_{33} - 2C_{13}^2 / (C_{11} + C_{12}) \quad (A11)$$

$$E_T = (C_{11} - C_{12}) [C_{33} (C_{11} + C_{12}) - 2C_{13}^2] / (C_{33} C_{11} - C_{13}^2) \quad (A12)$$